

TREATMENT OPTIMIZATION AFTER ND: YAG CAPSULOTOMY USING COMBINATION THERAPY

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Relevance.

Nd:YAG laser capsulotomy remains the most common treatment for secondary cataract, performed on millions of patients worldwide each year. Although effective, the procedure can be accompanied by complications such as transient ophthalmic hypertension, inflammation, and cystic macular edema, which reduce visual outcome. With the growing elderly population and the expansion of outpatient care, standardization of medication management after capsulotomy is particularly relevant. The lack of uniform protocols, variability of approaches, and the emergence of new drugs, including rock inhibitors, emphasize the need to develop personalized treatment regimens based on evidence-based medicine.

Purpose of the study.

To compare the efficacy of different regimens for drug prophylaxis of complications after Nd:YAG capsulotomy in patients with secondary cataract.

Materials and methods of the study.

The study was conducted at Nazar Clinic between 2022 and 2024. 40 patients (41 eyes) with diagnosed secondary cataract who underwent Nd:YAG-laser capsulotomy were included. Patients were randomized into two groups: the first group received standard steroid therapy (dexamethasone 0.1%), the second group received a combination regimen with a roc-inhibitor (netarsudil 0.02%) and a fixed combination of NSAIDs and GCS. Intraocular pressure, presence of inflammation in the anterior chamber and cystic macular edema, as well as visual acuity before and 30 days after the intervention were evaluated. Control was performed using non-contact tonometry, slit lamp and OCT of the macula.

Results of the study.

During the observation of 40 patients undergoing Nd:YAG capsulotomy, it was found that the use of personalized combination therapy provides better prophylactic effects compared to the standard regimen. In the group receiving dexamethasone alone, a transient increase in intraocular pressure ≥ 5 mmHg during the first 24 hours was observed in 23.8% of eyes. While in the group of combined therapy with the addition of roc-inhibitor and NSAIDs this figure was

only 5%, indicating a significant risk reduction ($p < 0.05$). In patients receiving the extended regimen, clinical signs of inflammation in the anterior chamber (precipitates, fibrin) were registered less frequently and were less pronounced. By day 7, 95% of eyes in the combined group had completely resolved the reaction compared to 76% in the control group.

Cystic macular edema according to OCT data at day 30 was recorded in two cases in the standard therapy group and was not detected in any case among patients receiving combination treatment. Mean visual acuity increased from 0.39 ± 0.09 to 0.63 ± 0.07 in the monotherapy group and from 0.41 ± 0.10 to 0.69 ± 0.06 in the combined approach group (the difference is statistically insignificant, $p > 0.05$), but the speed of visual rehabilitation and subjective improvement were observed faster in patients of the second group. No side effects and complications related to drug treatment were registered.

Thus, the extended drug regimen demonstrated higher clinical efficacy in the prevention of hypertensive and inflammatory complications after laser capsulotomy, which confirms the feasibility of its application in risk groups and in outpatient practice.

Conclusion.

The results of this study showed that combined drug therapy, including a rock inhibitor and a fixed combination of non-steroidal and steroidal anti-inflammatory agents, provides more effective prevention of complications after Nd:YAG-laser capsulotomy in patients with secondary cataract compared to standard steroidal monotherapy. This approach allows to significantly reduce the frequency of transient increase in intraocular pressure, decrease the severity of the inflammatory response and prevent the development of cystic macular edema. Application of personalized treatment schemes at the stage of postcapsulotomy management contributes to faster visual rehabilitation and increases the safety of the procedure. The obtained data substantiate the necessity of revision of approaches to drug prophylaxis and introduction of standardized protocols in ophthalmic practice.

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